

Aryl Derivatives from Castor Oil. Part I. Methyl Arylundecanoate and Phenylundecanol

H. N. ARSANIOUS and Z. SAWIRIS

Chemical Department, Ministry of Industry, Cairo, Egypt
and

F. G. BADDAR*

Department of Chemistry, Ain Shams University, Cairo, and Kuwait University, Kuwait

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The condensation products of methyl undecenoate with benzene, toluene, *m*-xylene, anisole and chlorobenzene, and of undecenyl alcohol with benzene using anhydrous aluminium chloride as condensing agent were oxidised by chromic acid. The resulting alkyl aryl ketones were analysed by GLC and were found to be a mixture of six isomers with aryl group on carbon 5 to carbon 10 of the paraffinic chain.

THE Friedel-Crafts reaction of methyl undecanoate with benzene and toluene was investigated by Achaya *et al.*¹, and Zeman *et al.*² Gas liquid chromatography of the distilled product from methyl undecanoate showed that it is a mixture of at least three isomers of methyl arylundecanoate presumably the 8-, 9- and 10-aryl-isomers¹. Methyl phenylundecanoate, however, when examined by capillary chromatography and mass spectrometry² was found to give five peaks, one of them representing the 5- and 6-phenyl isomers together (11.6%) and the other four representing 7-, 8-, 9- and 10-phenyl isomers (15.1%, 17.0%, 21.0% and 35.3% respectively).

In the present investigation gas liquid chromatography of the mixture of ketones obtained by chromic acid oxidation of methyl phenylundecanoate and phenylundecanol revealed six position isomers, with substitution at carbon atoms 5 to 10 for both the ester and the alcohol with a higher percentage of the 5-phenyl isomers in the case of the alcohol than in the ester. By this procedure it was possible to determine the percentage of the 5-phenyl and 6-phenyl isomers separately. This was not possible

by capillary chromatography on the methyl phenylundecanoate itself which gave one peak for the 5- and 6-phenyl isomers.

The isomeric distribution of methyl *p*-tolylundecanoate, *m*-xylylundecanoate, *p*-methoxyphenylundecanoate, *p*-chlorophenylundecanoate and phenylundecanol was also investigated.

Experimental

Starting materials: Undecenoic acid was prepared³ by the cracking of castor oil at 400°/2-3 mm. The crude acid was distilled and the fraction b.p. 152°-154°/3 mm was collected, esterified with methyl alcohol and 4% concentrated sulphuric acid, then fractionally distilled *in vacuo* to give methyl undecanoate, b.p. 102°/1.5 mm ($n_D^{25} = 1.4572$; I.v. = 127.8; sap. equiv. = 198).

Methyl arylundecanoate: Methyl undecanoate (19.8 g; 0.1 mole) was added dropwise during 30 min. to a stirred suspension of aluminium chloride (14.6 g; 0.11 mole) in the aromatic substrate (0.6 mole of benzene, toluene, *m*-xylene, or chlorobenzene)⁴. The products were fractionally distilled under reduced pressure, their characteristics are given in Table I.

TABLE I—METHYL ARYLUNDECANOATES

Ester (Mixture of isomers)	b.p. °C/mm	Refractive Index	M.W. (sap.equiv.)	M.W. (Calc.)
Methyl phenylundecanoate	140-160/1.5	1.4850	274.00	276
Methyl <i>p</i> -tolyl	162-176/2.0	1.4950	291.00	290
Methyl <i>m</i> -xylyl	164-176/2.0	1.4878	309.20	304
Methyl <i>p</i> -anisyl	178-184/2.0	1.4920	309.20	306
Methyl <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	194-210/2.0	1.5005	302.00	310

Undecenyl alcohols: Methyl undecenoate was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride following the procedure given by McCutcheon *et al.*⁵. The product was distilled to give undecenyl alcohol, b.p. 100°–110°/3 mm; $n_D^{25} = 1.4489$ (Found: OH, 9.6%; I.v., 148.0; Calc. for: OH, 9.98%; I.v., 149.4).

Phenylundecanols: A mixture of isomers was prepared by the following two different routes: (i) Phenylation of undecenyl alcohol in excess of benzene with anhydrous aluminium chloride. This gave a product, b.p. 160°–170°/1.5 mm (Found: OH, 6.77%; I.v., nil. Calc. for: OH, 6.84%; I.v., nil). (ii) The methyl phenylundecanoate, obtained by phenylation of methyl undecenoate, was reduced to give a mixture of isomeric phenylundecanols which was found to have the same physical constants as those of the product obtained by the first method.

Chromic acid oxidation: The oxidation was carried out as described by Smith, *et al.*^{6,7} by heating methyl arylundecanoate (1 mol) with chromic acid (6 mols) in glacial acetic acid (10 mols). The ratio of chromic acid was increased to 7 moles in the case of phenylundecanol to allow the oxidation of the primary alcoholic group. The oxidation product was washed with aqueous alkali to remove acid fraction, and the neutral fraction was subjected to gas liquid chromatography.

Alkyl aryl ketones: Acetophenone, propiophenone, butyrophenone, valerophenone, caprylophenone, heptophenone and their substitution products were prepared by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of the respective acid chlorides and the appropriate substrate^{8,9}.

Gas liquid chromatography: Methyl arylundecanoate, and phenyl undecanol were chromatographed using Pye Argon chromatograph (4 ft column with 10% Apiezon L or 10% polyethylene glycol adipate on celite 100–120 mesh). The number of peaks with the percentage of the corresponding components are shown in Figs. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 and Table 2. The alkyl aryl ketones resulting from oxidation of the arylundecanoate and phenylundecanol were also chromatographed using either Hewlett Packard Research dual column temperature programmed gas chromatograph Model 5750, with an 8 ft stainless steel column containing 25% silicone grease on celite 60–100 mesh or the above mentioned Pye Argon

Fig. 1. GLC of Methyl Phenylundecanoate.

Fig. 2. GLC of Methyl Tollyundecanoate.

Fig. 3. GLC of Methyl 2,4-Dimethylphenylundecanoate.

Fig. 4. GLC of Methyl Anisylundecanoate.

Fig. 5. GLC of Methyl Chlorophenylundecanoate.

Fig. 6. GLC of Phenylundecanol.

Peak	Methyl arylundecanoate					Phenylundecanol
	Ar = phenyl%	<i>p</i> -tolyl%	<i>m</i> -xylyl	<i>p</i> -anisyl	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	
1	28.0%	33.1%	46.4%	8.8%	34.4%	18.2%
2	14.3	20.3	14.0	7.3	23.2	21.5
3	17.0	16.6	20.1	17.8	19.5	21.8
4	40.7	4.5	19.5	47.6	5.4	38.5
5	—	17.5	—	7.8	12.9	—
6	—	8.0	—	10.7	4.6	—

TABLE 3—DISTRIBUTION OF ISOMERIC METHYL ARYLUNDECANOATE AND PHENYLUNDECANOL (Determined by GEC of the product of chromic acid oxidation)

Position of aryl group	Methyl arylundecanoate					Phenylundecanol
	Ar = phenyl	<i>p</i> -tolyl	<i>m</i> -xylyl	<i>p</i> -anisyl	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	
10	42.0%	20.6%	47.8%	48.3%	65.0%	41.40
9	13.4	4.4	9.9	26.6	6.3	6.6
8	14.4	6.2	9.9	16.3	8.0	7.5
7	15.8	15.0	13.4	6.3	19.6	12.3
6	12.0	18.0	19.0	2.5	10.1	13.2
5	2.4	35.8	—	—	—	19.0

chromatograph. The alkyl aryl ketones were identified by comparison with authentic samples *cf.* Table 3.

Discussion

Gas liquid chromatography of the distilled methyl arylundecanoate and phenyl undecanol revealed

that neither of them is a single component (*cf.* Figs. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 and Table 2). It was not possible to identify the different peaks representing the different isomers resulting from double bond isomerization or *o*- and *p*-substitution. However, direct oxidation followed by gas chromatography of the degradation products was applied to determine the structure of the isomers. Methyl phenylundecanoate

gave on oxidation a mixture of six alkyl aryl ketones, namely acetophenone (42.0%), propiophenone (13.41%), butyrophenone (14.4%), valerophenone (15.8%), caprylophenone (12.0%) and heptophenone (2.4%) (cf. Table 3). These arise from the oxidation of methyl 10-, 9-, 8-, 7-, 6-, 5-phenylundecanoate isomers, respectively. By this procedure it was possible to determine the percentage of the 5-phenyl and 6-phenyl derivatives separately, whereas gas capillary chromatography of methyl phenylundecanoate gave one peak for the 5- and 6-phenyl isomers.

Smith *et al.*⁶ prepared methyl phenylstearate from methyl oleate and reported that the phenyl attachment in the isomers would not progress further than carbon 6. They attributed this to the possible formation of a δ -lactone from the intermediate carbonium ion, thus preventing the carbonium ion from further isomerization.

Since the presence of methyl 5-phenylundecanoate has been proved in the present investigation, the formation of a stable γ -lactone cannot be overlooked. It is significant to point out that Placek and Bickford¹⁰ working on the hydroxylation of oleic acid showed that, through isomerization, the attachment of the hydroxyl wanders till carbon 5. This conclusion is also supported by the work of Zeman *et al.*³

The isomeric distribution of methyl *p*-tolylundecanoate, xylylundecanoate, anisylundecanoate, and chlorophenylundecanoate is reported in Table 3.

The isomeric distribution of phenylundecanol, prepared by the phenylation of undecenyl alcohol, as revealed by gas liquid chromatography of the ketones, obtained by chromic acid oxidation of the product was 19.0%, 13.2%, 12.3%, 7.5%, 6.6% and 41.4% for 5-, 6-, 7-, 8-, 9-, 10-phenyl isomers, respectively. It is obvious that in the phenylation of methyl undecenyl alcohol as compared with the phenylation of methyl undecenoate higher percentage of the 5-phenyl isomer (*aa*. 19.0%) was obtained (cf. Table 3). This may be attributed to the fact that lactone formation in the former case is impossible.

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